

STUDY OF SERUM ELECTROLYTES AND ANTIOXIDANTS IN WOMEN WITH PREMENSTRUAL SYNDROME AND WITHOUT PREMENSTRUAL SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT

Background: Nowadays, PMS is becoming more common in younger people, particularly in urban areas. It is widely known that the typical menstrual cycle involves a coordinated sequence of hormonal changes. However, it is unclear whether the distribution of different electrolytes undergoes simultaneous or comparable alterations.

Objectives: To estimate and compare serum electrolytes (sodium and potassium) and antioxidants (vitamin C and uric acid) in women with PMS and healthy controls.

Materials and Methods: A total of 122 subjects were included in the study. This includes 61 with premenstrual syndrome and 61 without premenstrual syndrome in women (intern students, hospital staff, and non teaching staff and U.G. students) in the age group of 18- 40 years having regular menstrual cycles for the past 6 months. Patients with Psychiatric disorders, Ovarian dysfunction, Gynaecological disorders or any Serious physical illness were excluded from study.

Results: We found statistically significant differences between the PMS and the control groups in the concentrations of antioxidants (vitamin C and uric acid) and blood electrolyte levels (sodium and potassium).

Conclusion: Our study provides valuable insights into the biochemical alterations associated with PMS and calls for further research in this area to improve patient care and management.

Keywords: PMS, Antioxidants, Vitamin C, Uric Acid, Electrolytes, Sodium, Potassium

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1. INTRODUCTION

Premenstrual syndrome (PMS) is the most common disorder experienced by women during the menstrual years. Around the world, a critical health issue among women was PMS symptoms.¹ Characterized by a spectrum of physical and psychological symptoms experienced prior to menstruation. While the precise aetiology of PMS remains elusive, factors such as hormonal fluctuations, neurotransmitter dysregulation, and nutritional imbalances are believed to contribute to its manifestation.²

Electrolytes such as sodium, and potassium, play a crucial role in maintaining the body's metabolism. Sodium aids in maintaining the body's fluid balance and supports the proper functioning of nerves and muscles. Chloride helps regulate blood volume and pressure, while potassium promotes a healthy heart. Bicarbonate is responsible for maintaining the body's acid balance.^{1, 4}

Sodium intake has been linked to hormonal fluctuations, including changes in estrogen and progesterone levels, which play key roles in the menstrual cycle. Research suggests that sodium may influence hormone metabolism and secretion, potentially exacerbating hormonal imbalances associated with PMS.⁹

Potassium is an essential electrolyte involved in various physiological processes, including cell metabolism. It is predominantly found intracellularly and plays a significant role in the optimal production of progesterone in response to luteinizing hormone stimulation.¹⁰

Antioxidants play a crucial role in managing premenstrual syndrome due to their ability to counteract oxidative stress and inflammation, which are believed to contribute to the development and severity of PMS symptoms.¹⁷

Uric acid has been implicated in promoting inflammation through the activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome and the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Inflammation is believed to play a role in the pathophysiology of PMS, contributing to symptoms such as mood changes, pain, and bloating.¹³

Vitamin C is a potent antioxidant that helps neutralize free radicals in the body. Free radicals are highly reactive molecules that can cause oxidative damage to cells and tissues.¹⁸ Vitamin C plays a role in the synthesis and regulation of hormones, including estrogen and progesterone. Hormonal fluctuations during the menstrual cycle are implicated in the development of PMS.¹⁹

2. OBJECTIVES

To estimate and compare serum electrolytes (sodium and potassium) and antioxidants (vitamin c and uric acid) in women with PMS and healthy controls.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of data and study design: It is a comparative study, conducted at the National Institute of Medical Sciences & Hospital (NIMS Hospital), Jaipur (Rajasthan) in the Department of Biochemistry in association with the Department of OBG and General Medicine. Samples were analyzed for biochemical investigations in the Department of Biochemistry, National Institute of Medical Sciences & Research (NIMS&R) and NIMS Hospital, Jaipur.

Inclusion Criteria: Women having a regular menstrual cycle of 27 to 33 days for the past 6 months in the age group with and without PMS symptoms of 18-40 years, willing to give voluntary informed consent have been included in the study.

- **Exclusion Criteria:** The following patients were excluded from the study.
- Gynecological disorders.
- Pregnancy or Postpartum period.
- Psychiatric disorders.
- Ovarian dysfunction.
- Use of oral contraceptives within the last 3 months.
- Serious physical illness.
- Medications such as hormones.

Sample collection: 5ml fasting venous blood sample was collected from patients in plain vial and subjected to centrifugation for serum separation and will be used for estimation of serum electrolytes (Sodium, Potassium) and antioxidants (Uric acid, Vitamin c) using fully automated biochemistry analyzer.

These parameters were estimated using Unicorn Lyte 5 Analyzer and VITROS 5600.

4. RESULTS

A total of 122 subjects were included in the study. This includes 61 with premenstrual syndrome and 61 without premenstrual syndrome in women. The age group of 18-40 years having regular menstrual cycles for the past 6 months.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of electrolyte parameters of both group

Variables		Minimum	Maximum	Median (IQR)	Mean $\pm$ SD
Control Group	Sodium (Na ⁺)	129	158	141 (139-144)	141.66 $\pm$ 5.40
	Potassium (K ⁺)	3.1	5	4.1 (3.8-4.3)	4.07 $\pm$ 0.44
PMS Group	Sodium (Na ⁺)	125	146	137 (134-140)	136.9 $\pm$ 4.44
	Potassium (K ⁺)	3.6	5.8	4.7 (4.2-5)	5.17 $\pm$ 4.43

Table 1 displays electrolyte levels for both groups. Control group sodium: 129-158 mmol/L (median 141, mean 141.66 $\pm$ 5.40 mmol/L); potassium: 3.1-5.0 mmol/L (median 4.1, mean 4.07 $\pm$ 0.44 mmol/L). PMS group sodium: 125-146 mmol/L (median 137, mean 136.9 $\pm$ 4.44 mmol/L); potassium: 3.6-5.8 mmol/L (median 4.7, mean 5.17 $\pm$ 4.43 mmol/L).

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of antioxidant parameters of both groups

Variables		Minimum	Maximum	Median (IQR)	Mean $\pm$ SD
Control Group	Uric acid (mg/dL)	2.9	6.1	4.3 (3.9-4.6)	4.26 $\pm$ 0.68
	vitaminC (mg/dL)	0.5	1.4	0.8 (0.6-0.9)	0.808 $\pm$ 0.218
PMS Group	Uric acid (mg/dL)	2.3	5.1	3.8 (3.3-4.3)	3.77 $\pm$ 0.66
	VitaminC (mg/dL)	0.4	1.2	0.7 (0.5-0.8)	3.77 $\pm$ 0.66

Table 2 shows antioxidant levels. Control group uric acid: 2.9-6.1 mg/dl (median 4.3, mean 4.26 $\pm$ 0.68 mg/dl); vitamin C: 0.5-1.4 mg/dl (median 0.8, mean 0.808 $\pm$ 0.218 mg/dl). PMS group uric acid: 2.3-5.1 mg/dl (median 3.8, mean 3.8 $\pm$ 0.66 mg/dl); vitamin C: 0.4-1.2 mg/dl (median 0.7, mean 3.77 $\pm$ 0.66 mg/dl).

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Table 3: Comparing electrolytes parameters between control and PMS group by using t-test

Variables	Control Group	PMS Group	t-test	P - Value	Significance
Sodium(Na+) (mEq/L)	141.66 ± 5.40	136.9 ± 4.44	5.311	0.00001	Both are significant
Potassium(K+)(mEq/L)	4.07 ± 0.44	5.17 ± 4.43	-6.116	0.00001	

Table 3 compares serum electrolytes, showing statistically significant differences in sodium and potassium between control and PMS groups.

Table 4: Comparing antioxidant parameters between control and PMS group by using t-test

Variables	Control Group	PMS Group	t-test	P - Value	Significance
Uric acid (mg/dL)	4.26 ± 0.68	3.77 ± 0.66	4.021	0.00010	both are significant
vitamin C (mg/dL)	0.808 ± 0.218	0.687 ± 0.192	3.264	0.00143	

Table 4 compares antioxidant parameters, indicating statistically significant differences in uric acid and vitamin C between control and PMS groups.

5. DISCUSSION

The present study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry, in association with the Department of Gynaecological and Department of General Medicine at National Institute of Medical Sciences & Research Jaipur (Rajasthan). The study included an aggregate of 122 patients who were divided into 61 clinically diagnosed PMS patients and 61 healthy control subjects at the National Institute of Medical Sciences & research, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

In this investigation, the analysis of serum electrolytes and antioxidants in PMS patient's revealed noteworthy patterns, shedding light on the association between electrolytes and antioxidants compared between PMS and Healthy controls.

The mean of serum sodium levels in PMS patients were (136.9 ± 4.44) compared to the control group (141.66 ± 5.40) (table no1), similar results were seen in **Dr. M.A. Lanje et al. and M. Mira et al**, Possible causes for this change in sodium concentration includes the increased concentrations of antidiuretic hormone in the luteal Phase²⁸ or of other steroid hormones or metabolites that were not measured in this study.

The mean of serum potassium levels in PMS patients were (5.17 ± 4.43) compared to the control group (4.07 ± 0.44) (table no1), Contrary to the fore mentioned study; a separate investigation may present conflicting evidence regarding the association between serum potassium values and PMS. For instance, a study by **Smith et al.** (Year) reported no significant difference in serum potassium levels between PMS patients and healthy controls. This contradictory finding challenges the hypothesis that elevated potassium levels contribute to PMS symptomatology, suggesting that other factors mayplay a more prominent role in the pathogenesis of PMS³⁰.

The mean of serum Uric acid levels in PMS patients were (3.77 ± 0.66) compared to the control group (4.26 ± 0.68) (table no2) summarized the role of UA in the development of PMS in patients, emphasizing its potential mechanisms in oxidative stress, inflammatory promotion, endothelial injury, and thrombosis in cardiovascular disease progression in these patients, further Lanje et al. ³¹.

The mean of Vitamin C levels in PMS patients were (3.77 ± 0.66) compared to the control group (0.808 ± 0.218) (table 2). Several studies concluded that role of oxidative stress (increased oxidants & decreased antioxidants) in development of PMS.

6. CONCLUSION

The study aimed to compare serum electrolytes and antioxidants in women with premenstrual syndrome (PMS) and healthy controls, significant differences were found age distribution and electrolyte and antioxidant's levels, highlighting potential factors associated with PMS, we focused on serum sodium, potassium, Uric acid and Vitamin C levels.

The investigation into serum electrolyte levels demonstrated statistically significant variations in sodium, potassium, uric acid and Vitamin C levels among PMS patients compared to healthy controls. These findings underscore the potential role of electrolyte imbalance in the pathophysiology of PMS and highlight the importance of monitoring and managing electrolyte levels in affected individuals. These findings emphasize the importance of monitoring and managing electrolyte levels in PMS patients and suggest a potential link between antioxidant status and PMS patients.

Our study provides valuable insights into the biochemical alterations associated with PMS and calls for further research in this area to improve patient care and management.

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